

THE INFLUENCE OF NICENE THINKING FOR CHRISTIAN FAITH FROM AN ASIAN/INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: Theologizing is a hermeneutic enterprise that is traditional, creative, and contextual. The Indian/Asian way of thinking cannot be deaf to the vibrations of the *divine Logos* in the Sacred Scriptures, the *groaning of the Spirit* in the agonies of the millions of the ‘crucified people.’ For Christian faith in the Indian and Asian context, Nicene theology remains not just a doctrinal anchor but also a powerful witness to the incarnation of God in Christ (Light from Light) as the hope and healing of the world.

Keywords: The Council of Nicaea, The Divinity & Humanity of Jesus, Light from Light, Asian/Indian Contextual Theology, Inculturation, Incarnation, Crucifixion & Resurrection.

INTRODUCTION

This article argues that, Nicene thinking did not only challenge the Arian heresy but also responded, often indirectly, to various religious and philosophical assumptions prevalent in the East, such as Docetism, Gnosticism, and dualistic metaphysics. These assumptions have parallels in Hindu, Buddhist, and other Eastern traditions, which often conceive of the divine as impassible, non-material, and ultimately beyond historical engagement. One of the central affirmations of the Nicene Creed is that Jesus Christ is “begotten, not made, being of one substance with the Father.” This assertion directly countered Arianism, which held that

Christ, as the Logos, was the highest of created beings but not truly divine. If Christ were not fully divine, he could not be the mediator between God and humanity. From an Indian perspective, where divine manifestations or avatars (such as Krishna or Rama) are understood as temporary and illusory appearances of God (*maya*), this Christian affirmation takes on new relevance. The idea that God could fully become human in a real, historical, and material sense challenges the common Eastern notion that the ultimate divine reality (such as Brahman) is beyond form (*rupa*) and name (*nama*), and can only take on appearances, not actual substance.

Closely related to this is the issue of Docetism—a heresy that claimed Jesus only seemed to be human, denying the reality of his physical body and suffering. While Docetism arose within the early Christian context, its assumptions resonate with certain strands of Indian philosophy that view the material world as an illusion (*maya*) and thus see human suffering, embodiment, and death as beneath the divine. Against this, the Nicene affirmation that Jesus is “God from God, Light from Light, true God from true God” insists on the real, tangible humanity of Jesus. He is not an appearance or an avatar but God incarnate—truly human, fully engaged in historical and material existence.

The Gnostic worldview, which also influenced early Christian thought and was firmly rejected by the Church, similarly held a dualistic view of the world in which matter was evil and spirit was good. This dualism has echoes in various Indian philosophies, such as certain interpretations of *Samkhya*, which view material existence (*prakriti*) as something to be transcended. Gnosticism could not accept that God could take on a material body, as it would imply contamination with evil. But the Nicene Creed insists on the goodness of creation and the full assumption of human nature, including the physical body, by the divine Logos. The Incarnation, then, becomes a divine affirmation of the material world—not something to be escaped, but something to be redeemed.

Another point of tension between Eastern thought and Nicene Christianity concerns the impassibility of God—the

idea that God cannot suffer or be affected by the world. In many strands of Indian and Asian religious thought, God is changeless, untouched by the suffering and flux of the world. The incarnation, then, seems not only impossible but also undesirable. However, Nicene Christianity affirms that in Jesus, God does suffer—though not in His divine nature, He suffers in His fully assumed human nature. This is not a contradiction but a mystery grounded in the unity of the person of Christ. The affirmation that “for our salvation he came down from heaven... and was crucified under Pontius Pilate” roots God’s action in real human suffering and history. It proclaims that divine love is not remote or detached but enters into the pain and brokenness of the world.

From an Indian worldview that often sees time as cyclical and ahistorical, the Nicene emphasis on the historical nature of the incarnation is striking. In many Eastern religions, time is understood in terms of recurring cycles (*samsara*), and the ultimate goal is to escape the cycle of rebirth. Human history, in this view, is not the locus of ultimate meaning. By contrast, the Nicene Creed locates the redemptive act of God in a specific historical moment—Jesus was “crucified under Pontius Pilate.” This historical grounding affirms that time and history matter. God acts within human history, not apart from it. This stands as a radical challenge to the timeless, ahistorical understanding of spiritual reality prevalent in much of Indian and Asian metaphysics. For Christian faith in the Indian and Asian context, Nicene theology remains not just a doctrinal anchor but also a powerful witness to the incarnation of God in Christ as the hope and healing of the world.

1. THE EARLY CHRISTIAN PRESENCE ON ASIAN SOIL

After the apostles, the Christians who came to India were from the Eastern Christian communities from Persia and Armenia to Kerala. Among them Thomas of Cana who came in the fourth century, and Sapor and Prot who came in the ninth century were instrumental in founding

Christian community in Kodungalloor.¹ Robin Boyd observes, “Although the Syrian Christian community has been culturally integrated with Indian society, there has been little or no attempt to work out a theology in Indian terminology... it has remained entirely Syrian, based on the Syriac language.”² J.B. Chethimattam attests,

Original contributions to Christology or to any branch of theology from the ancient Church of the St Thomas Christians Malabar were scant. Away from the centres of Christianity, it was not involved in the Trinitarian or Christological controversies that rocked the early church....³

2. THE INFLUENCE OF NICENE THINKING ON ASIAN SOIL IN THE 15TH CENTURY

Even though Christian presence existed right from the first century in India, only with the arrival of missionaries from Portugal and later France, Roman Catholicism was established and Protestantism followed in the eighteenth century, initially through the work of German Lutheran missionaries and East India Company chaplains. The missionaries like St. Francis Xavier, Thomas Stephens, Hieronymus Xavier, Robert de Nobili, John Calmette, Beschi, Johann Ernst Hanxleden, also known as Arnos Pathiri in India, Desideri in Tibet, Matteo Ricci in China, and Korean Yi-Piek in his native tongue, developed Christian faith along the lines of Nicene thinking .

2.1 Robert De Nobili

De Nobili studied the religious literature of the Hindus with reverence and respect.⁴ De Nobili evolved a theological structure for communicating the Christian faith and coined

¹ Cf. L. Fernando and G. Gispert-Sauch, *Christianity in India: Two Thousand Years of Faith* (New Delhi: Penguin/Viking, 2004), 55.

² R. Boyd, *An Introduction to Indian Christian Theology* (New Delhi: ISPCK, 2000), 9.

³ J.B. Chethimattam, “Indian Approaches to Christology: Contribution of the Syro-Malabar Church,” *IJT* 23 (1974): 176.

⁴ Cf. R. de Smet, “Robert de Nobili as Forerunner of Hindu-Christian Dialogue,” *Hindu-Christian Studies Bulletin* 4 (1991): 2.

terminology for Christian theology in the Indian context.⁵ His specific contribution along the lines of Nicene thinking is his concept of Christ as *Satguru*. De Nobili understands that Jesus is incarnate *Guru* who teaches men and women the way to attain the shores of heaven (*Moksa*).⁶ D. Jeyaraj quoting De Nobili enunciates,

With body I am sending you to the world. There going about as a *Guru*, show all men [and women] clearly by your conduct and words, that they must renounce all that is sin, and that they must walk in the path of virtue so that they may attain the shores.⁷

To establish Jesus as *Satguru*, De Nobili makes a critical distinction between *Avatara* and Incarnation. Since *Avatara* means descent, he accepts the term but distinguishes the Hindu *Teva avataram* (divine descent) and the Christian *Manusa Avataram* or descent into a human form, by which the divine Word takes on a complete human nature (*parikkirakam ceytal*), whereas the power of Vishnu rests on *Krsna* and takes on only a human body. He criticizes in the light of his conviction that to be human one must be a unity of soul and body. He rejects the idea of many *Avataras* in both human and animal forms as superfluous and disrespectful to God. The goal of incarnation is to save and divinize all so that they share the very goodness and beatitude of God. It takes place through the virginal conception and birth of Jesus. De Nobili describes God is the invisible *Guru*, Christ the visible *Satguru*, the divine *Guru* (*Tevaguru*) or Messiah (*Teyva kuru*). Like a dancing master teaching his pupils a dance, the Supreme *Guru* (*Paramakuru*) became man, teaches all men and women the dance of virtue (*Punniya natanam*) by his own dance of virtue.⁸

⁵ J. Thekkedath, *History of Christianity in India, Vol II* (Bangalore: Theological Publications of India, 1982), 73, cited in Sebastian C. H. Kim (ed.), *Christian Theology in Asia* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2008), 43.

⁶ D. Jeyaraj, “The Contribution of the Catholic Church in Tamilnadu in the 17th-19th Centuries to an Understanding of Christ,” *IJT* 23 (1974): 185.

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ S. Arockiasamy, *Dharma, Hindu and Christian, according to Robert de Nobili* (Documenta Missionalia Series 19; Roma: Editrice Pontificia Universita Gregoriana, 1986), 162.

2.2 Matteo Ricci

The Chinese meet Jesus of the Nestorian Church and call him *Misia* (Messiah), one who saves the people from the Sea of Suffering. *Misia* is a Buddhist word that is associated with *Meitreyā* (Messianic Buddha). Matteo Ricci tried very hard to reach a pivotal point of contact between the Chinese and the Christians, between Confucius' teachings and Jesus' teachings. For example, when Matteo Ricci introduced Nicene understanding of Jesus as truly divine and truly human, East Asians could not catch this, but understood Jesus as a human with a spirit (Jesus, the crucified and risen sage – *sheng* and Jesus the Way – *dao*).⁹

3. THE INFLUENCE OF NICENE THINKING ON ASIAN SOIL IN THE 18TH & 19TH CENTURIES

It is interesting to note that in Asia, Christology was first formulated by Hindus who encountered Christianity through the colonial enterprise. In other words, there was a “reception” of the message of Christ but in Hindu terms.¹⁰ Countries like China, Taiwan, Japan, Thailand, Korea, Indonesia under the influence of Hinduism, Buddhism, Islam, Confucianism, and Taoism wished to interpret the message of Christ in their own experiences. For example, a South Korean theologian Chung Hyun Kyung spoke of the Holy Spirit in the image of *Kuan Yin*, the Chinese female *bodhisattva* symbol of compassion, who is revered not only in China, but also in Japan, Korea, Singapore, and Vietnam.

3.1 Keshub Chunder Sen

Keshub Chunder Sen saw Jesus Christ as an oriental and responded to him with great devotion. He perceived Jesus as “divine humanity,” the second person of the Trinity – *Logos Incarnate*.¹¹ Sen enunciates *Logos* in terms of

⁹ Roman Malek (ed.), *The Chinese Face of Jesus Christ*. Vols. 1 & 2 (Sankt Augustin: Institut Monumenta Serica and China-Zentrum, 2002), 2003.

¹⁰ M.M. Thomas, *The Acknowledged Christ if the Indian Renaissance* (Bangalore: CISRS, 1970).

¹¹ K.C. Sen, *Lectures in India* (Calcutta: Navavidhan Publication 1954), 368.

“*Saccidananda*.” God the Father, the Creator, is the *Sat*; the Son, the Logos is the *Cit*; and the Holy Spirit, the Sanctifier, is the *Ananda*. The descending God is the Logos, the word.¹² Sen is critical of the Indian concept *Avatara* because it's a crude representation of the ascending scale of divine creation rising from the lowest scale of life through the fish, the tortoise, and the hog, up to the perfection of humanity. Jesus Christ is the culmination and crown of this continued evolution of the Logos.¹³ Sen stressed that Jesus remained truly man even after his resurrection and ascension into heaven. In him, the human nature is perfected by true affiliation to the Divine nature. He shows us how we can exalt our humanity by making it more and more divine. He came to lead humanity into Divinity.

3.2 Brahmabandhab Upadhyay

Brahmabandhab Upadhyay describes ultimate reality as “*Saccidananda*” which parallels the Christian Trinity of the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit.¹⁴ His aim was to restate his understanding of the Logos in the terms of *Advaita*, while still being faithful to the Nicene-Constantinople Creed.¹⁵ Upadhyay's interpretation of Jesus Christ reflects St. Thomas Aquinas' thought of God as the most universal of all causes and the universal effect is being-existence. Christ is the wisdom and Word of God by which He understands Himself. The Holy Spirit proceeds from God's love of Himself and makes us lovers of Him.¹⁶ Upadhyay accomplishes this through, the *Vedantic* concept of *iksana*, setting forth the distinction between *Parabrahman* and *Sabdabrahman*. For him, *Para Brahman* is identified with the Father and the object of His knowledge, *Cit*, is reproduced as *Sabdabrahman*, which

¹² K.C. Sen, *Keshub Chandra Sen's Lectures in India II* (London: Cassell, 1904), 17.

¹³ Boyd, *An Introduction to Indian Christian Theology*, 28.

¹⁴ Julius Lipner, *Brahmabandhab Upadhyay: The Life and Thought of a Revolutionary* (Delhi: OUP, 1999), 178.

¹⁵ T.C. Tennet, *Building Christianity on Indian Foundations: The Legacy of Brahmabandhab Upadhyay* (Delhi: ISPCK, 2005), 237.

¹⁶ *Summa Theologica*, I, 16.4, 45.5.

Upadhyay identifies with Logos. Logos as the “mystery of the timeless Word-colloquy... the eternal, intellectual act of divine generation.”¹⁷ Secondly, Upadhyay uses *Vedantic* teaching concerning the five sheaths (*kosa*) of human nature as found in the *Taithiriya Upanisad*¹⁸ From this understanding of the nature of human, Upadhyay explains the *hypostatic union* of divine and human natures in Jesus Christ the God-Man.¹⁹ Upadhyay’s theology is best reflected in his Sanskrit hymn, which he composed to the Incarnate Logos. The hymn is clearly Christocentric, reflecting Nicene structure of Christian experience expressed within the stream of Indian cultural, religious language, thought and history.²⁰

The transcendent Image of Brahman,
 Blossomed and mirrored into the full-to-overflowing
 (*upachita*)
 Eternal knowledge (*chirachit*), Victory to God, the God-
 Man.
 Child of the pure Virgin, Guide of the Universe, infinite in
 being
 Yet beauteous with relations, Victory to God, the God-Man.
 Ornament of the Assembly of saints and sages,
 Destroyer of fear, chastiser
 Of the Spirit of Evil,-Victory to God, the God-Man.
 Dispeller of weakness of soul and body,
 pouring out life for others,
 Whose deeds are holy? Victory to God, the God-man.
 Priest and Offerer of his own soul in agony,
 whose Life is Sacrifice?
 Destroyer of sin’s poison, Victory to god, the God-Man.
 Tender, beloved, Soother of the human heart,
 Ointment of the eyes,
 Vanquisher of fierce death, Victory to God, the God-Man.²¹

¹⁷ Tennet, *Building Christianity on Indian Foundations*, 237.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ B. Upadhyay, *The Twentieth Century* (1901), 7. Cf. Boyd, *An Introduction to Indian Christian Theology*, 80.

²⁰ G. Gispert-Sauch, “The Sanskrit Hymns of Brahmabandhav Upadhyay,” *RS* 19/4 (1972): 74.

²¹ *Ibid.*

4. THE INFLUENCE OF NICENE THINKING ON ASIAN SOIL IN THE 20TH CENTURY

Though we cannot be exhaustive in this section, it will be useful to illustrate thoughts and concerns of a few thinkers.

4.1 George Soares-Prabhu

George Soares-Prabhu, a perceptive Biblical theologian, restored the term *Sadguru* in the most absolute sense, Jesus as the “Incarnate Guru.” For Soares-Prabhu, Jesus Christ, the second person of the holy Trinity is God and man, and is the only and unique incarnation of God. He rejects the idea of many *avataras*. Soares-Prabhu considers Jesus as an authoritative Lord, as the Teacher of Righteousness and the Saviour from Sin who illuminates as well as instructs and communicates not just knowledge but salvation. Soares-Prabhu regards that *Abba* experience of Jesus is the starting point of the *Dharma* of Jesus understood both as the *Dharma* which he practiced (Jesus’ *Dharma*) and the *Dharma* he preached (Christian *Dharma*). Soares-Prabhu understood *dharma* as a socio-ethical order geared towards the holistic sustenance of the individual and society.²² Sonship of Jesus makes him mediator between God and human beings. Because of this *dharma* of Sonship, Jesus is the very revelation of God (cf. Mk 1:35-39; 2:13-17; 6:34; 10:45). “Looking at his life we know what God is like”; and “looking at his life we know what man can be like.” *Dharma* of Sonship stands in contrast to the *dharma* of the Law. The *dharma* of Sonship implies a fraternity of humankind and gives rise to the *dharma* of concern:

Being Son once again makes little sense if one were to understand it in a static metaphysical sense (*homoousios*). Being Son cannot be separated from showing concern for others sons and daughters. The damage that the metaphysical theologies have done to Christian faith is immense. Such theologies seek to define everything (including God)

²² George Soares-Prabhu, “The Dharma of Jesus: An interpretation of the Sermon on the Mount,” *Bible Bhashyam* 6 (1980): 358-381.

conceptually in a static way, without feeling obliged to do justice to the dynamic character of the mystery. In such understanding the Son is Son because he is generated eternally from the Father, and shares his substance.²³

4.2 Samuel Rayan

Samuel Rayan argues that the Nicene-Chalcedon approach for an Indian context must begin with the indwelling Christ who is the real, best, and deepest self. From there, he proceeds to the Christ who is in all and is the Self of all, the Universal Self and the *Antaryamin*. It is the Holy Spirit which develops the idea of a new community. One of the richest Indian words incorporated into the Christian vocabulary is the compound “*Saccidananda*” to designate the mystery of the Blessed Trinity. *Sa tredha atmanam vyakuruta* –“He revealed Himself in a Trinitarian way” (BU 1, 2.3).²⁴ The Divine Reality is not only a Presence as the Ground of our being, but also the Power that promotes and guides the conscious life that flows within us. There is an *antaryamin*, the “Inner Controller,” the Ultimate Subject in all our subjective acts. He is in us not as object but as subject and this is the way, we enter into deepest union with the Divine. St. Paul too spoke of the “inner Teacher,” Christ, who is the ground or possibility upon which all human knowledge rests. “It is no longer I who live, but it is Christ who lives in me” (Gal 2:20) and “the mystery of Christ” is defined in a later writing as “Christ in you, the hope of glory” (Col 1:27). Especially our life of faith is a life produced by the *antaryamin* Spirit: “When we cry, ‘Abba, Father!’ it is that very Spirit bearing witness to our spirit that we are children of God” (Rom 8:15-16).

4.3 Aloysius Pieris

A Sri Lankan Jesuit sat at the feet of the Theravada Buddhist tradition and relentlessly pitched for an Indic cultural way as an alternative path for encountering, understanding, and expressing the mystery of redemption with the eyes on Calvary where, in a

²³ Joseph Lobo, *Encountering Jesus Christ in India* (Bangalore: ATC, 2005) 362.

²⁴ Raimon Panikkar, *The Rhythm of Being: The Gifford Lectures* (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 2010), 230.

historically recorded set of political circumstances, *sub Pontio Pilato*, Jesus revealed himself as the Christ, the Messiah, the Liberator in the context of a social conflict. Pieris holds that the use of dogma is vague for Indic mind, instead one should use *sutra*. *Sutra* is more evocative rather than merely declarative. One has to admit that the ancient dogmatic Christological definitions expressed in categories of Greek philosophy and anthropology are unrelated to the frames of Indic mind. The reflections on incarnation were an after-thought of those who had grasped the meaning of the Cross as the summit of the redemptive process and as the privileged locus of exaltation. The Cross is a social location where a social conflict unfolds between God and the Mammon. Hence, any reflection on Christ is a programme of liberation, which simultaneously generates a theology, and not a speculation.²⁵ For Christians in Myanmar the Cross of Christ is the locus to break the social boundaries and embrace Buddhists into the inclusive community.²⁶

4.4 Michael Amaladoss

Amaladoss argues the clear definition of Nicene-Chalcedon is not quite intelligible in India. Some of those terms cannot even be translated in Indian languages. He suggests that the mystery of Jesus as a story to be inter-religious and inter-liberative, creating space for other believers:

Jesus challenges us to turn back to history. God is authentically encountered today, not in ‘sacred mysteries’, but in the poor and the marginalized to whom the Reign of God is proclaimed and in whom it is slowly taking shape. The criterion of the truth of God’s humanity in Jesus is not abstract dogmas but a community that opts for the poor and does justice, respecting the divine and human freedoms operative in history leading it to a fulfillment that we can only affirm in faith and hope.²⁷

²⁵ Aloysius Pieris, “Christ Beyond Dogma: Doing Christology in the Context of the Religions and the Poor,” *Logos* 39/3 (2000): 23-28.

²⁶ David Thang Moe, “Exclusion and Embrace: A Theology of Breaking Boundaries and Building Bridges between Christianity and Buddhism in Myanmar,” *Exchange* 46 (2017): 127.

²⁷ M. Amaladoss, “Who Do You Say That I Am?,” *VJTR* 60/12 (1996): 784-789.

4.5 Kim Chi Ha

Korean Minjung theology highlights that Jesus himself was the victim of dominant powers – *sub Pontio Pilato*. In a poem entitled “The Golden-crowned Jesus,” Kim Chi Ha presents Christ crowned with gold pleading with a person suffering from leprosy, a beggar, and a prostitute, to help him to be free. The Cross is the irony of God’s wisdom on the powerful. The Cross painted on Christian ballet-masks in Korea represents the *minjung*, angry and sad, ironic and laughing. Because of the Cross, the people can laugh both at their own suffering and at the rich, just as Jesus derided the Pharisees (Mt 23).²⁸ We see this similarity in the struggles of Filipino people and relate to Jesus as *Kuya* (Older Brother) deeply involved in their pain and suffering.²⁹

5. ‘LIGHT FROM LIGHT’: A HERMENEUTIC KEY TO UNDERSTAND THE INFLUENCE OF NICENE THINKING IN ASIA

Vatican II states, “In every nation the capacity to express Christ’s message in its own fashion is stimulated and at the same time a fruitful interchange is encouraged between the church and various cultures” (GS 44). The Christian experience of faith in Jesus Christ stretches across the centuries, but is inseparable from its plural forms of faith, says Avery Dulles.³⁰ A long Trinitarian and Christological discussions in the early Christianity culminate in the Council of Nicaea, which is a structure of Christian religious experience.³¹

The hermeneutic key to understand the influence of Nicene thinking for Christian faith in Asia/India is the symbol/metaphor of ‘**Light from light,**’ itself. In Asian/

²⁸ David Kwang-Sun Suh, *The Korean Minjung in Christ, The Christian Conference of Asia* (Hong Kong: Christian Conference of Asia, 1991), 168.

²⁹ Eleazar S. Fernandez, *Toward a Theology of Struggle* (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1994), 101f.

³⁰ Avery Dulles, *The Changing Forms of Faith, The Survival of Dogma* (Garden city, NY: Doubleday, 1971), 17-31.

³¹ William P. Loewe, *Introduction to Christology* (Quezon City: Claretian Publications, 1996), 193.

Indian cultures, we are familiar with symbols and images of community’s experiences of the living Christ.³² Jaroslav Pelikan points out that Jesus cannot be understood outside human cultures and that it is human cultures that shape the diverse images and understanding of Jesus in human history.³³ Pope Leo XIV in his first Apostolic Visit to Nicaea said,

the Christian faith must always be expressed in the languages and the categories of the culture we live, just as the Fathers did at Nicaea and other councils. At the same time, we must distinguish the essence of faith from the historical formulas that express it – formulas that are always partial and provisional and can change as doctrine is more deeply understood.³⁴

We observed that, De Nobili described Jesus as the perfect *Sadguru*. Upadhyay used a classic Indian metaphor, calling Christ an ‘ornament’ or alternatively ‘a radiant gem,’ the ‘destroyer’ of darkness. It’s often forgotten that the celebrated formula ‘**Light from light**’ is itself an interpretation of Scripture. The Word is light and his Sonship and divinity entail that God the Father is also light.³⁵ In the words of the Letter to the Hebrews, Jesus is “the brightness of his glory” (1:3).³⁶ The biblical texts speak, “God is light and in him is no darkness” (1 Jn 1:5); “In thy light we shall see light” (Ps 36:10); Wisdom is “the radiance of the eternal light” (Wis 7:26); The Word “was the true Light, which lights everyone that comes into the world” (Jn 1:9); “I am the light of the world: the one who follows me shall not walk in darkness, but shall have the light of life” (Jn 8:12). Irenaeus

³² Stanley E. Porter, Michael A. Hayes & David Tombs (eds.), *Images of Christ: Ancient and Modern* (England: Sheffield Academic Press, 1997), 128-189.

³³ Jaroslav Pelikan, *Jesus through the Centuries: His Place in the History of Culture* (New Haven: Yale University Press), 1985.

³⁴ Pope Leo XIV, “Apostolic Visit to Nicaea,” <https://www.romereports.com/en/2025/11/28/pope-leo-xiv-warns-against-the-resurgence-of-old-heresies-there-is-a-new-arianism/> (accessed on 29.12.2025).

³⁵ Isidoros Charalampos Katsos, “‘Light from light’: The metaphysics of light of the early church,” in T. T. Clark, *Handbook of the Early Church* eds. Ilaria L.E. Ramelli, J.A. McGuckin and Piotr Ashwin-Siejkowski (New York: Bloomsbury, 2023), 466.

³⁶ Athanasius, *Defence of the Nicene Definition* 3.12.

of Lyons and Origen surprisingly develop “Christology of epiphany.”³⁷ Origen’s *De Principiis* richly dwells on the theme of ‘light.’ He speaks of God through the ‘radiance’ of Light because God is the ‘radiance’ itself. In the final state of union with God in knowledge and desire, all intellectual creatures will be united with each other, by sharing as one in God’s incorruptible and eternal light and thus share God’s uniquely spiritual way of being.³⁸ St. Augustine affirms that the purpose of the Incarnation made the humans sharers in God’s immortality – “deification” or “divinization.”³⁹ Here is how St. Athanasius articulated: “For he was made [hu] man that we might be made God,” and “he himself has made us sons [and daughters] of the Father, and deified men [and women] by becoming himself man.”⁴⁰

The theme of “light” reflects ‘sun simile’ at the end of the sixth book of Plato’s Republic, which entered biblical reflection through the medium of Hellenistic Judaism. Indian Sacred texts richly communicate the use of fire and light. *Agnim ile purohitam*: “I venerate fire, the high priest,” says the *Rg Veda* (1.1.1a). *Tamasoma jyotirgamaya*: “From the Darkness Lead me towards the Light” (BAUp, 1:3.28). The festival of *Diwali* (a row of lights) symbolizes God is Light. The synonymous use of fire and light is found in Greek culture and the double sense of ‘light’ as either the light-ray or light-source is essential part of the fourth-century trinitarian debates.⁴¹ “The One Real (Light/Truth) the sages call by many names – *ekam sat vipra bahudha vadanti*, or in another version, *ekam santam bahudha kalpayanti*” (RV, X:114.5). Clement of Alexandria (150-

³⁷ Brian E. Daly, *God Visible: Patristic Christology Reconsidered* (London: Oxford Press, 2019), 66f.

³⁸ Brian E. Daly, “Incorporeality and ‘Divine Sensibility’: The Importance of *De Principiis* 4,4 for Origen’s Theology,” *Studia Patristica* 41 (2006): 139-44.

³⁹ David Maconi, “St. Augustine’s Early Theory of Participation,” *Augustinian Studies* 27 (1996): 81-98.

⁴⁰ Athanasius of Alexandria, *On the Incarnation of the Word* 54.3.

⁴¹ Jarslov Pelikan, *The Light of the world: A Basic Image in Early Christian Thought* (New York: Harper, 1962), 26-33.

216 CE) would affirm, “For what is One is indivisible and thereby infinite.”⁴² Manikka Vacagar in *Tiruvacagam* writes: “In mercy affable, and sweetest grace transcending thought, In light He came, caused light within my soul to shine. Light of my soul, thrilling my flesh and inmost frame, – Thou art! Civan is my Light who brought joy to my heart.”⁴³ *Arul* (grace/light) liberates the soul from *anavam* (darkness). That is why J.C. Beschi addressed Jesus in *Tembavani* as “*Neeye Arulkadal*” – “Ocean of Light” (grace). In the Liturgical, hymn “*Veni Sancte Spiritus*,” we read *Et emitte coelitus-Lucis tuae radium*. St. Thomas Aquinas asked: *Infundere digneris super intellectus mei tenebras tuae radium claritatis* – “Deign to pour forth on the darkness of my intellect one ray of your light.”⁴⁴

God is a mystery, the Unknown. He is Light. In the Indian/Asian cultures, God is utter darkness not because God is darkness but the effulgence of Light appears as darkness. St. Paul says, “He lives in an inaccessible light.” St. Gregory the Great spoke of God as “uncircumscribed Light (*lumen incircumscriptum*).” The inaccessible light is the description of darkness for human and at the same, the light brings transformation and gives warmth. Hence mystics often speak of their journey into God in terms of ‘dark night of the soul,’ ‘living flame’ (St. John of the Cross), ‘inner space’ (St. Clare), and ‘dance of ecstasy’ (Mira Bai). “Of his fullness we have all received, grace upon grace” says John (Jn 1:16), which is not so distant from the Upanishadic affirmation, *etasya eva anandasya anyani matram bhutani upajivanti* – “all other beings live upon a mere portion of that Ananda,” the Absolute Brahman (BAUp. 4.3.32).⁴⁵ Paul, the Apostle articulates, “participation in Christ’s death (darkness) now is but a prelude to sharing in his resurrection

⁴² Clement Of Alexandria, *Stromata*, 5.12.

⁴³ As Quoted in Christina Manohar, *Spirit, Time and Eternity: East-West Reflections* (Delhi: ISPCK, 2015), 103.

⁴⁴ As Quoted in Vandana Mataji, “The Power of the Holy Spirit,” *VJTR* 62/1 (1998): 45.

⁴⁵ G. Gispert-Sauch, “Notes for an Indian Christology,” *VJTR* 61 (1997): 761.

(light) later.”⁴⁶ Vatican II noted “...the mystery of [wo] man is seen in its true light only in the mystery of the Word incarnate” (*Gaudium et spes*, no. 22). Jesus is “our common name and common hope.”⁴⁷ St. Basil the Great of Caesarea writes:

When a sunbeam falls on a transparent substance, the substance itself becomes brilliant, and radiates light from itself. So too Spirit-bearing souls, illumined by Him, finally become spiritual themselves, and their grace is sent forth to others... the presence of God, becoming like God, and, the highest of all desires, becoming God.⁴⁸

Hence, any genuine objective dialogue of the Christian concept of incarnation and of the Hindu concept of *Avatara* must show that God incarnate – ‘**Light from light.**’ Certainly, the leveling of the two concepts is not correct. The term ‘*avatara*’ may convey what the Christian creed affirms of Christ: “came down from heaven.” It need not do so, for the ‘descent’ implied may not be more than an “earthly manifestation,” some kind of ‘theophany.’ According to Gispert-Sauch, the word *avatara* implies a point of departure and a descending movement (compare the concept of *katabasis* in the Church Father, the ‘condescension’ of God to our world), perhaps with a certain connotation of triumph.⁴⁹ In all events, the term “*avatara*” is not equivalent to the term ‘incarnation,’ which implies a real becoming. Incarnation is not a mythic caricature of “God in a human costume,” “God who has put on a body,” in the words of Karl Rahner.⁵⁰

⁴⁶ Michael J. Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord: A Theological Introduction to Paul and His Letters* (Michigan: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2004), 302f.

⁴⁷ Ignatius of Antioch, *Ephesians*: 10;1.2.

⁴⁸ As Quoted in Michael J. Christensen and Jeffrey Wittung, *Partakers of the Divine Nature: The History and Development of Deification in the Christian Traditions* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Publishing Group, 2007), 23.

⁴⁹ Noel Sheth, “Hindu Avatara and Christian Incarnation: A Comparison,” *VJTR* 67 (2003): 183-193.

⁵⁰ Karl Rahner, “Current Problems in Christology,” *Theological Investigations, I: God, Christ, Mary and Grace* (London: Darton, Longman and Todd, 1961), 156.

The Incarnate Crucified guru (*sub Pontio Pilato*) is in the midst of suffering people.⁵¹ Participation in the people’s struggle for justice and freedom are theological events, articulating the theology latent in them to understand its in-depth the nature (why and how God suffers), to see its affinity to ultimate realities and meanings, to sustain the hope of God’s Reign on the Earth and to keep the combat human.⁵² Gispert-Sauch argues, bliss can exist even in the state of *dukkha* and *soka* (suffering and sorrow), indeed even in the abandonment of the cross: “Father, in your hands I commend my spirit.” Jesus possesses from his very birth [Incarnation] the fullness of joy [love], the Spirit, but it remains unmanifest until the moment of his death and resurrection when it explodes to pervade all the layers of his being and indeed to spread to the whole Universe in spiritual wave after wave.

Indic world-view doesn’t have the theological concept of resurrection, but on the contrary longs for release from birth (*punarjanma*). The life of resurrection is essentially a life of the Spirit—a completely spiritualized existence. This is what the Hindu soul seeks an awakened existence beyond space and time.⁵³ It is in and through the resurrection, the word-flesh (humanity) continues to relate to human beings, who turn to him in faith.⁵⁴ The resurrection is a guarantee that Christ (*Lumen Christi*), the new man, remains permanently at work in the world through the Spirit. Incarnation, then, is not confined to those years of his earthly pilgrimage but is extended to all time; and its consummation is still to be achieved when God will be all in all. The Risen Christ dwells in us through the power of His Spirit and so our ‘*atman*’ can be united with His *atman*. This upward aspiration to

⁵¹ Johann Baptist Metz, *A Passion for God: The Mystical-Political Dimension of Christianity* (ed. and trans. J. Mathew Ashley; New York: Paulist Press, 1998), 163.

⁵² S. Rayan, “People’s Theology,” *JD* (1992): 202.

⁵³ X. Irudayaraj, “An Attempt at an Indian Christology,” *Indian Ecclesiastical Studies* 9 (1970): 17-18.

⁵⁴ Ysabel De Andia and Peter Leander Hofrichter, *Christus bei den Vaetern* (Innsbruck: Tyrolia, 2004), 11f.

be children of God is the reality of the *Jivatman* and is its response to the *Paramatman*. The Risen Christ is the divine Light in which we Christians “discern the signs of God’s presence and power” in the historical process (GS 11, 22). In the words of John Kakichi Kadowaki, a Japanese Jesuit, “Jesus Christ as the way [Light] is seen both creator of all things, and a fundamental force setting history in motion as well as an inner moving power and ultimate goal leading ‘all human beings as wayfarers’ to salvation.”⁵⁵

CONCLUSION

The Nicene Creed stands as a profound and counter-cultural affirmation—not only within the early Christian context but also when viewed through the lens of Indian and broader Eastern thought. Its insistence on the full divinity and full humanity of Christ challenges both the Arian denial of Christ’s divinity and the Docetic and Gnostic denials of his real humanity. Against philosophies that see the material world as illusory or corrupt, the Creed declares that God truly entered into time, history, and human flesh—not as an appearance or symbol, but as a redemptive act rooted in love. The Christian claim that God became fully human without ceasing to be fully divine offers a striking theological vision: one in which suffering, embodiment, and history are not barriers to the divine but the very arenas of God’s salvific work. In a cultural and religious context shaped by ideas of *maya*, impassibility, and cyclical time, the Nicene Creed offers a distinct and transformative proclamation—that in Jesus Christ, God has embraced the material world to redeem it, and that human history, far from being an illusion to escape, is the very place where divine love is made manifest.

⁵⁵ John Kakichi Kadowaki, “From Chuang tzu’s Way to Jesus Christ as the Way,” *Inter-Religio* 15 (1989): 2-20.